

A whole lotta jars: revision of the historical wet collections of the Museu de História Natural e da Ciência da Universidade do Porto

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The historical collections of the Museu de História Natural e da Ciência da Universidade do Porto (MHNCUP), Portugal, represent an important but yet understudied scientific heritage. These collections, which data back to the late nineteenth century, are some of the most important natural history collections in the country. They have had a pivotal role for the development of zoological sciences in late nineteenth/early twentieth century Portugal, as well as to teaching of natural history in the University of Porto. The MHNCUP collections are constituted by the typical assortment of categories of specimens present in most natural history collections: herbaria, mounted taxidermies, study skins, pinned insects, osteological collections, shells, fluid preserved specimens, etc.

The “wet collections”, constituted by specimens preserved in different types of fluid preservatives (from formalin to ethanol) represent a considerable part of the zoological collections (over 5000 jars), ranging from invertebrates, fishes, amphibians and reptiles, birds and mammals. Besides the presence of some more recent specimens, most of the collection dates back to the late 1890’s to 1930’s.

Following decades of abandonment and improper curation, the wet collections are now being reviewed, recatalogued and recovered. In this presentation we aim to present an overview of collections in terms of taxonomic coverage, origin of the specimens, the diversity of type of jars present in the collections, the preservatives used, the main conservations problems and the subsequent adopted solutions to its recovery and curation. This represents a study case on the recovery of an entire historical liquid collections, as well as can serve an illustrative example on what a “typical” late nineteenth/early twentieth century wet collections looks like.

